
PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT OF AN INDUSTRY: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to improve the performance of a forging unit. Now a day, flexibility in manufacturing industries with the help of the smaller batch size has been increased drastically. To compete in market the industries are focused on quick change over time. SMED (Single Minute Exchange of Die) is a technique used in lean manufacturing. This paper explains a case of SMED technique applied on die setting of 6.25 T hammer in a forging industry. By using SMED tool such as Kaizen, 5S and visual management setup time is to get reduced by 14 minutes (from 85 minutes to 71 minutes).The percentage reduction in set up time is 16.47 %.

KEYWORDS- SMED, External and internal operation, Die History card